

Damping of Oscillations in Multi Machine Integrated Power Systems by SSSC based Damping Controller Employing Modified Genetic Algorithm

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Abstract : In this paper, an investigation into the use of modified Genetic Algorithm optimized SSSC based controller to aid damping of low frequency inter-area oscillations in power systems is presented. Controller design is formulated as a nonlinear constrained optimization problem and modified Genetic Algorithm (MGA) is employed to search for the optimal controller parameters. For evaluation of effectiveness and robustness of proposed controllers, the performance was tested on multi-machine system subjected to different disturbances, loading conditions and system parameter variations. Simulation results are presented to show the fine performance of the proposed SSSC controller in damping the critical modes without significantly deteriorating the damping characteristics of other modes in multi-machine power system

Keywords : SSSC, FACTS, controller design, damping of oscillations, multi-machine system, Modified Genetic Algorithm (MGA).

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